

Synthesis and characterization of glycine substituted cyclotriphosphazene

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Abstract : Glycine substituted adduct of $(\text{PNCl}_2)_3$ was synthesized and characterized on the basis of qualitative, quantitative, TLC, FTIR and mass spectral analysis. The chemical data assigned as $(\text{P}_3\text{N}_3)_2\text{H}_2(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COO})_8\text{NHCH}_2\text{COO}$, having NHCH_2COO -bridging between two (P_3N_3) rings along with other glycinic group linked to P atom of P_3N_3 rings.

Keywords : Phosphazenes, amino acid, glycine.

Introduction

Due to N atom, $(\text{NPCl}_2)_3$ molecule has much coordinating property, so, it has formed a large number of complexes with metals¹⁻⁶. On the other hand, there are six symmetric chlorine atoms which perform substitution reaction with covalent compounds⁷. These substituted and adducted derivatives of $(\text{NPH}_2)_3$ have industrial, pharmaceutical and biological importance such as, the complexes of $(\text{NPCl}_2)_3$ with Cu, Fe and Co are found bactericidal⁸⁻¹⁰. Adducts of $(\text{NPCl}_2)_3$ with phenoxy substituted compound are hydraulic lubricant¹¹. Poly organophosphazenes have fire proofing agents¹², plastics¹³ and biological properties¹⁴. While polymethoxy, ethoxy amino and aryl substituted polyphosphazene are bioactive¹⁵. Pt^{II} complex of $(\text{NPCl}_2)_3$ has antitumor activities¹⁶. Polyamino phosphazenes are found germicide¹⁷⁻²⁰. Water soluble cyclotriphosphazenes(diamine) Pt^{II} conjugated drugs are also found having antitumor activity²¹.

Results and discussion

The phosphazinides adduct of glycine is brownish colored, insoluble in water but soluble in hydrazine. Its melting point is 184–186 °C which is entirely different than the reactants. The presence of amino acid, glycine, NH_4^+ and PO_4^{3-} for P_3N_3 rings was found positive during qualitative analysis. The gravimetric estimations show % found C, 23.51; O, 30.8; N, 22.43; P, 19.87 ± 1 and H, 3.84 and mol. wt. 939 g/mol, formulating the adduct

as $(\text{P}_3\text{N}_3)_2\text{H}_2(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COO})_8\text{NHCH}_2\text{COO}$ which is supported by the mass peak m/z 939 ($m+2$) in its DART mass spectrum. The other mass lines in its mass pattern (Fig. 1) are for the different fragments (Table 1) expounded on the basis of FAB fragmentation process as shown in Scheme 1.

Thus the chemical data obtained by quantitative estimations are in close agreement to those calculated from the mass spectrum, confirming its above molecular formula.

Further to confirm the formation of adduct and bonding in it, the FTIR spectrum of the adduct is compared to IR spectrum of glycine and $(\text{PNCl}_2)_3$. The vibration at 520.8–673.0 cm^{-1} for P-N (ring) band, at 903.4–979.9 cm^{-1} for N-H₂ band at 1079.7 cm^{-1} for -NH-CH₂- band, at 1182.5 cm^{-1} for -NH-CH₂- (bridging) band, at 1407.0–1471.7 cm^{-1} for -P-O, a doublet at 1664.8–1714.7 cm^{-1} for -OC=O band, 2365.0 cm^{-1} for -P=N(ring) and at 3436.0 cm^{-1} for -N-H- band have been observed in its IR spectrum (Fig. 2, Table 2).

Thus two P_3N_3 rings have linked to each other by -NHCH₂COO- group, which is acting as bridge between them. The other glycinic groups are attached with remaining P-atom of the P_3N_3 rings as expressed by structure (Fig. 3).

To know the nature of the bonding, the force constants are calculated by the using of following formulae²³ :

Scheme 1

Fig. 1. Mass spectrum of compound.

Table 1. Mass spectral data

Sl. no.	m/z	Fragments	Remarks
1.	73.11	NHCH ₂ COO	
2.	202.12	H ₃ P ₃ N ₃ O ₄	
3.	228.10	P ₃ N ₃ O ₂ H(CH ₂ .COO) (m+2)	
4.	273.16	N ₃ P ₃ O(NHCH ₂ COO).COO (m+2)	

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

5.	324.24	$N_3P_3(NHCH_2COO)_2 \cdot NHCO$ (m-2)
6.	340.23	$N_3P_3(NHCH_2COO)_2NHCH_2CO$
7.	640.31	$(N_3P_3)_2(NH_2CH_2COO)_4 \cdot (NHCH_2COO)$ (m+1)
8.	714.99	$(P_3N_3)_2(NH_2CH_2COO)_5(NHCH_2COO)$ (m+1)
9.	784.28	$(P_3N_3)_2H_2(NHCH_2COO)_6(NHCH_2COO)$ (m-3)
10.	866.72	$(N_3P_3)_2H_2(NH_2CH_2COO)_7(NHCH_2COO)$ (m+3)
11.	939.37	$(P_3N_3)_2H_2(NH_2CH_2COO)_8(NHCH_2COO)$ (m+2)

Fig. 2. IR spectrum of compound.

Table 2. IR spectral data

Sl. no.	Frequency of bands (cm^{-1})	Bands assigned	Force constants ($dyne/cm^2$)
1.	520.8-673.0 (w,b)	P-N (ring)	$1.56 \times 10^4 - 2.61 \times 10^4$
2.	903.4-979.9 (b)	-NH ₂	$4.36 \times 10^4 - 5.33 \times 10^4$
3.	1079.7 (s)	-NH-CH ₂ -	4.45×10^5
4.	1182.5 (b)	-CH ₂ -NH- (bridge)	5.34×10^5
5.	1407.0-1471.7 (w,s)	=P-O-	$1.24 \times 10^6 - 2.29 \times 10^6$
6.	1646.8-1714.3 (s)	-OC=O	1.19×10^6
7.	2365.0 (s)	-P=N (ring)	3.23×10^5
8.	3436 (b)	-N-H--	6.56×10^5

Fig. 3. Proposed structure of the compound $(P_3N_3)_2H_2(NH_2CH_2COO)_8NHCH_2COO$.

$$\bar{\nu} = 1/2\pi c \sqrt{k/\mu}$$

where k = force constant, μ = reduce mass,

$$\frac{1}{\mu} = \frac{1}{m_1} + \frac{1}{m_2} + \dots$$

The values of force constant have inferred the presence of P-N and P=N groups. And broad band at 3436.0 cm^{-1} for N-H band having the H-bonding between N-atom of glycine and P-H of P_3N_3 rings.

The formation of compound may be explained by the following reaction :

The structure of the compound may be expressed as Fig. 3.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Phosphorous pentachloride, amino acid (glycine), ammoniumchloride, chlorobenzene, ether, alcohol, etc. well doubly distilled chemicals were used.

Preparation of hexachlorocyclotriphosphazene :

$(\text{PNCl}_2)_3$ was prepared by the refluxing of equimolar mixture of PCl_5 and NH_4Cl in chlorobenzene at $140\text{--}160 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 7–8 h. The unreacted NH_4Cl was removed by filtration and $(\text{PNCl}_2)_3$ was obtained, after distillation under reduced pressure.

Preparation of amino acid (glycine) substituted phosphazene :

The compound of glycine with $(\text{PNCl}_2)_3$ was prepared by the refluxing a mixture of $(\text{PNCl}_2)_3$ and glycine (100 mg of each in 1 : 1) at $140\text{--}150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 7–8 h using $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$ as solvent. A brownish precipitate obtained, which was filtered, washed with chlorobenzene, ether and alcohol. Dried product was stored in vacuum desiccator over fused CaCl_2 .

Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer was used to record the IR spectrum ($4000\text{--}500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The DART mass spectrum was recorded on a JEOL-Accut of JMS-T1001c mass spectrometer having a DART source using helium lamp at $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Micro-analysis for constituted elements was got done from CDRI, Lucknow, mol. wt. was determined by Rast's method.

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